

Low Circulating Free Triiodothyronine Levels are Associated with the Progression of Diabetic Nephropathy in Patients with Type 2 Diabetes

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Abstract:

Background: Diabetic nephropathy is a leading cause of end-stage renal disease in patients with diabetes. Recent studies suggest that low circulating free triiodothyronine (fT3) levels may be associated with the progression of diabetic nephropathy.

Aim: To evaluate the association between low circulating free triiodothyronine levels and the progression of diabetic nephropathy in patients with type 2 diabetes.

Methods: A prospective cohort study was conducted at Rajshree Medical Research Institute, Bareilly, UP, from April 2023 to April 2024. Ninety patients with type 2 diabetes were enrolled. Data on fT3 levels, HbA1c, serum creatinine, and urinary albumin-to-creatinine ratio (UACR) were collected. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0.

Results: Low fT3 levels were significantly associated with the progression of diabetic nephropathy ($p < 0.01$). Patients with low fT3 levels had a higher rate of nephropathy progression (70%) compared to those with normal (30%) or high fT3 levels (10%). A negative correlation ($r = -0.65$, $p < 0.01$) was observed between fT3 levels and nephropathy progression.

Conclusion: Patients with type 2 diabetes are more likely to experience the advancement of diabetic nephropathy if they have low levels of circulating free triiodothyronine. In these individuals, keeping an eye on and controlling fT3 levels may be essential to preventing renal decline.

Recommendations: To better understand the underlying mechanisms and potential treatment strategies that target thyroid hormone levels in diabetic nephropathy, more research is required.

Keywords: Diabetic Nephropathy, Type 2 Diabetes, Free Triiodothyronine, Thyroid Hormones, Renal Function.

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Introduction

One of the main complications of diabetes mellitus that greatly increases the morbidity and death rate of the condition is diabetic nephropathy. Increased cardiovascular risk, a decrease in glomerular filtration rate (GFR), and persistent albuminuria are its defining characteristics. The increasing global prevalence of diabetic nephropathy emphasises the need for efficient management techniques and early detection to stop the illness's development to end-stage renal disease (ESRD). Triiodothyronine (T3), one of the thyroid hormones that is primarily studied, is involved in the control of glucose metabolism and renal function. The active thyroid hormone triiodothyronine (T3) is essential for growth, development, and metabolic functions. Low levels of free triiodothyronine (fT3) in individuals with chronic kidney disease (CKD) have been linked to unfavourable outcomes, such

as elevated cardiovascular mortality and the advancement of renal disease [1].

Research has demonstrated that patients with diabetes frequently have low fT3 levels, which are linked to a higher risk of complications from their diabetes. For example, the development of diabetic nephropathy has been associated with low fT3 levels; this association has been attributed to multiple possible processes. According to one study, patients with lower fT3 levels than those with normal fT3 levels were substantially more likely to develop diabetic nephropathy. This association remained after controlling for variables that could have caused confusion, including age, body mass index (BMI), length of diabetes, and glycaemic management [1].

There are several different mechanisms at play in this relationship. The pathophysiology of diabetic

nephropathy involves endothelial dysfunction, inflammation, and altered renal haemodynamics, all of which may be influenced by low fT3 levels. Thyroid hormones also affect glucose metabolism and insulin sensitivity, two other important aspects of the onset and course of diabetic kidney disease [2].

These results suggest that measuring fT3 levels in type 2 diabetic individuals can provide important information about their chance of developing diabetic nephropathy. Interventions targeted at preserving or regaining normal fT3 levels may also slow the development of renal failure in this population.

The purpose of this research is to learn more about the connection between type 2 diabetic patients' developing diabetic nephropathy and low levels of free triiodothyronine in the blood.

Methodology

Study Design: This is a prospective cohort study aimed at evaluating the association between low circulating free triiodothyronine (fT3) levels and the progression of diabetic nephropathy in patients with type 2 diabetes.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at Rajshree Medical Research Institute, Bareilly, UP, from April 2023 to April 2024.

Participants: A total of 90 participants with type 2 diabetes were recruited for the study.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Patients diagnosed with type 2 diabetes.
2. Age between 35-70 years.
3. Both male and female patients.
4. Patients with documented diabetic nephropathy stages 1-3.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Patients with other types of diabetes.
2. Patients with thyroid disorders or those on thyroid medications.

3. Pregnant women.
4. Patients with acute or chronic infections.
5. Patients with severe cardiovascular, hepatic, or other systemic diseases.

Bias: To minimize bias, random sampling was employed, and all assessments were performed by blinded investigators. Confounding factors such as age, gender, BMI, and duration of diabetes were controlled during data analysis.

Data Collection: Data was collected through patient interviews, medical records, and laboratory tests. Blood samples were collected to measure fT3 levels, HbA1c, serum creatinine, and urinary albumin-to-creatinine ratio (UACR).

Procedure

1. Initial assessment of all participants, including demographic data and medical history.
2. Baseline laboratory tests to determine fT3 levels, HbA1c, serum creatinine, and UACR.
3. Follow-up assessments every 3 months to monitor changes in nephropathy stages and fT3 levels.
4. Data was recorded and managed using standardized forms and electronic databases.

Statistical Analysis: Data analysis was done with SPSS 23.0. To compile the data, descriptive statistics were employed. For categorical variables, chi-square tests were employed, while t-tests or ANOVA were utilised for continuous variables. The association between the development of diabetic nephropathy and fT3 levels was assessed using regression analysis and Pearson correlation. Statistical significance was attained when the p-value was less than 0.05.

Results

Participant Characteristics: A total of 90 participants with type 2 diabetes were included in the study. The baseline characteristics of the participants are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1:

Characteristic	Value
Total Participants	90
Mean Age (years)	58.4 ± 10.2
Gender (M/F)	50/40
Mean HbA1c (%)	8.1 ± 1.5
Mean fT3 (pmol/L)	3.5 ± 0.6
Baseline UACR (mg/g)	200 ± 50
Mean Duration of DM (years)	12.4 ± 5.6

Table 2: Association Between fT3 Levels and Nephropathy Progression

Group	Mean fT3 (pmol/L)	Progression of Nephropathy (%)
Low fT3 (<3.0 pmol/L)	2.5 ± 0.3	70%
Normal fT3 (3.0-4.0 pmol/L)	3.5 ± 0.2	30%
High fT3 (>4.0 pmol/L)	4.5 ± 0.3	10%

These tables illustrate the baseline characteristics of the study participants and the significant association between low FT3 levels and the progression of diabetic nephropathy, underscoring the potential role of thyroid hormone monitoring in managing diabetic kidney disease.

Discussion

This study examined the relationship between patients with type 2 diabetes and low levels of circulating free triiodothyronine (FT3) and the development of diabetic nephropathy. Ninety people participated in the study, which revealed a substantial correlation between a higher rate of nephropathy progression and lower FT3 levels. To be more precise, nephropathy progressed in 70% of patients with low FT3 levels (<3.0 pmol/L), 30% of patients with normal FT3 levels (>4.0 pmol/L), and 10% of patients with high FT3 levels (>4.0 pmol/L).

Lower FT3 levels are associated with an increased risk of disease development, according to correlation analysis, which found a substantial negative connection ($r = -0.65$, $p < 0.01$) between FT3 levels and the advancement of nephropathy. Even after adjusting for other factors like HbA1c and the length of diabetes, regression analysis demonstrated that low FT3 levels were an independent predictor of the development of nephropathy. According to these results, keeping an eye on and controlling FT3 levels may be essential to keeping type 2 diabetic patients' kidneys from failing.

Significant evidence has been found in recent research between patients with type 2 diabetes with the development of diabetic nephropathy (DN), which is characterised by low circulating free (FT3) levels. Serum FT3 levels in patients with DN were considerably lower than in patients without DN, according to a thorough investigation involving 400 patients. The results of the investigation showed a negative correlation between DN progression and decreased FT3 levels, suggesting a possible involvement of thyroid hormone in the pathogenesis of DN [3].

In another study, 421 euthyroid people with type 2 diabetes were examined, and it was discovered that those with DN had far lower FT3 levels. This cross-sectional investigation confirmed the link between thyroid hormone levels and kidney disease in diabetics by demonstrating an inverse relationship between FT3 levels and the occurrence of DN [4].

Additionally, the relationship between thyroid hormone levels and the likelihood of diabetic kidney disease (DKD) progression was investigated. According to the study, certain FT3 thresholds have been identified as essential markers

for higher risk of developing DKD. Low FT3 levels were revealed to be significant predictors of DKD progression. According to these results, FT3 levels may be useful markers for tracking kidney health in diabetes patients [5].

Low FT3 levels have also been connected to other diabetes problems besides nephropathy. A study with 2477 in patients with type 2 diabetes found a strong correlation between diabetic peripheral neuropathy (DPN) and lower levels of FT3. This study emphasises the larger significance of thyroid hormone levels in diabetes-related problems, even though it did not discover an association with carotid atherosclerotic lesions [6].

Moreover, in addition, a cross-sectional study involving 1071 euthyroid individuals with type 2 diabetes revealed a negative correlation between DN and FT3 and FT4 levels, but a positive correlation between TSH levels and DN. The significance of thyroid function monitoring in patients with diabetes is highlighted by this study, which supports the idea that low thyroid hormone levels are substantially linked to an elevated risk of DN [7].

Conclusion

The study's findings emphasise the necessity of routinely measuring thyroid hormone levels in people with type 2 diabetes, especially in those who have the condition or are at risk of getting diabetic nephropathy. Therapeutic measures intended to preserve or return FT3 levels to normal may slow the advancement of renal disease and enhance patient outcomes. To further understand the underlying mechanisms and create tailored treatments that address the interaction between thyroid hormones and diabetic nephropathy, more study is required.

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